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Analysis of Regulatory and Discretionary Powers of the CBN Over Financial Institutions Under BOFIA 2020

¹Shuaibu Lawal Abubakar ²Gadzama, Christopher Linus & ³ThankGod Okeokwo,

¹Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna, Nigeria
,+2347035682009 lawalshuaibu2014@gmail.com;

^{2,3}Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria
²+2348033077037 gadzamabob@gmail.com
³+2348039316857 barrthankgodokeokwo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research critically examines the regulatory and discretionary powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) over financial institutions under the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020. Employing a doctrinal methodology, the study draws upon statutory provisions, judicial interpretations, and scholarly commentaries to analyse the extent, scope, and implications of the CBN's authority. It interrogates the balance between ensuring financial stability and preventing excessive concentration of power in the regulatory framework. The findings reveal that BOFIA 2020 significantly strengthens the supervisory and interventionist role of the CBN, empowering it to revoke licences, impose sanctions, regulate corporate governance, and take control of distressed institutions without recourse to courts in certain circumstances. While these provisions enhance efficiency in regulatory response, they also raise concerns about arbitrariness, lack of transparency, and potential conflicts with principles of natural justice. The study recommends the establishment of clearer checks and balances on the exercise of CBN's discretionary powers, including mandatory judicial or legislative oversight for critical interventions such as licence revocations. It also proposes enhanced stakeholder engagement, transparency frameworks, and periodic independent reviews of the CBN's regulatory actions to foster accountability. In conclusion, while BOFIA 2020 equips the CBN with robust tools to safeguard the financial system, the sustainability of these powers depends on striking a balance between effective regulation and the protection of institutional and investor rights.

Keywords: Regulatory, Discretionary, Powers, CBN, BOFIA

1. INTRODUCTION

The financial system constitutes the backbone of every modern economy, providing the framework for mobilizing savings, facilitating investment, and ensuring efficient allocation of resources.¹ In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) occupies a pivotal position as the principal regulator and supervisor of financial institutions, particularly banks and other licensed operators. The Bank and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020 represents a landmark legislative framework which strengthens the CBN's regulatory and discretionary powers over financial institutions in line with

¹LLB, BL, LLM in-view,

²Lecturer 1, LLB, BL, LLM, PhD in-view

²Lecturer 1, LLB, BL, LLM, PHD in-view

¹ SO Alode, *The Nigerian Financial System at a Glance* (CBN 2017)

contemporary realities of the global financial system. The Act replaced the earlier BOFIA of 1991, introducing more robust provisions aimed at safeguarding financial stability, protecting depositors, and enhancing the soundness of the banking sector. The rationale for conferring broad powers on the CBN arises from the systemic nature of the financial sector and the devastating consequences that institutional failures can inflict on the wider economy.² Nigeria's experience with banking crises in the 1990s and the 2008 global financial meltdown underscored the need for proactive regulation, timely intervention, and adequate supervisory discretion. BOFIA 2020, therefore, expands the CBN's authority to license, regulate, monitor, and, where necessary, sanction financial institutions. It also provides the Bank with extensive discretionary powers to issue guidelines, conduct special examinations, revoke licenses, assume control of failing institutions, and prescribe prudential standards. These powers are intended to ensure that financial institutions operate within the bounds of safety, stability, and integrity.³

The regulatory and discretionary powers of the CBN under BOFIA 2020 are not without controversy. On one hand, they are indispensable for maintaining confidence in the financial system, promoting macroeconomic stability, and aligning Nigeria's banking practices with international standards such as the Basel frameworks.⁴ On the other hand, concerns have been raised regarding the breadth of these powers, the potential for arbitrary exercise, and the implications for institutional autonomy and due process. The Act gives the CBN Governor significant latitude in decision-making, sometimes without recourse to judicial oversight, which has generated debate among legal scholars, practitioners, and stakeholders in the financial sector. The provisions of BOFIA 2020 have significant implications for corporate governance, investor protection, and the balance between regulatory authority and institutional independence. The CBN's capacity to impose penalties, dictate capital adequacy ratios, and even restructure failing banks places it at the centre of Nigeria's financial policy architecture.⁵ While these measures may be justified on prudential grounds, they raise questions about accountability, transparency, and the extent to which the discretionary powers should be subject to checks and balances.

The introduction of BOFIA 2020 thus reflects both Nigeria's response to domestic financial challenges and its attempt to align with global regulatory best practices. It highlights the tension between the need for strong central regulation and the risks of over-concentration of authority in a single institution. This study therefore examines the scope, nature, and implications of the regulatory and discretionary powers of the CBN over financial institutions under BOFIA 2020.⁶ It interrogates whether these powers strike an appropriate balance between ensuring financial stability and respecting the rights of financial institutions, and further considers the safeguards necessary to prevent abuse of discretion while sustaining public confidence in the banking sector.

2. Conceptualising Regulatory and Discretionary Powers of Central Bank of Nigeria

The concepts of regulatory powers and discretionary powers are central to the functioning of administrative and financial law, particularly in the oversight of sensitive sectors such as banking and finance.⁷ They describe the scope of authority granted to a public body, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), to maintain order, protect the public interest, and ensure the stability of financial institutions under enabling legislation like the Bank and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020.⁸ Regulatory powers refer to the statutory authority vested in a regulator to make rules, issue directives, monitor compliance, and enforce standards within a defined sector. They are exercised pursuant to enabling legislation and are generally specific, structured, and mandatory in character. For instance, under BOFIA 2020, the CBN is empowered to license banks, prescribe prudential

² CB Onyido, 'The role of the Central Bank in the Nigeria financial system' *CBN Digital Commons* (2004)(28)(1)

³ BA Oke, 'The evolution of the Nigerian Financial System: problems challenges and prospects' *CBN Economic and Financial Review* (1989)(27)(2)

⁴ M Uche and O Oluwademilade, *Banks and other Financial Institutions Act 2020: The Making of a Super Regulator in Nigeria (1)* (SPA Ajibade & Co, 2020)

⁵ A Olaniwun, *The Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act 2020-Spotlight on Notable Provisions* (Newsletter 2020)

⁶ KPMG, *BOFIA 2020: Impact on the Financial Services Industry* (KPMG Nigeria 2021)

⁷ MJ Aljaber and AM Al-Raqqad, 'The discretionary powers of the civil judge in determining to approve the use of personal evidence as a mean of proof or not' *Journal of Legal Ethical and Regulatory Issues* (2021)(24)(7)

⁸ HO Eromosele, 'Central Banking and Regulations' *Federal University Otuoke Journal of Management Sciences* (2023)(7)

guidelines, set capital adequacy requirements, approve mergers or acquisitions, and enforce sanctions for violations. These powers are primarily supervisory, ensuring that financial institutions operate within prescribed norms to guarantee financial soundness, consumer protection, and systemic stability. Regulatory powers are thus exercised to achieve uniform compliance and predictability in the system.⁹

Discretionary powers, on the other hand, denote the legal authority conferred on a regulator to make decisions based on judgment, expediency, or policy considerations within the scope of the law.¹⁰ Unlike regulatory powers, they are not strictly prescriptive but allow room for flexibility in interpretation and application. For example, the CBN's discretion to revoke a banking license, assume control of a failing institution, or impose administrative penalties is guided by statutory provisions, but the timing, extent, and nature of such intervention often rest on the regulator's assessment of prevailing circumstances. Discretionary powers are necessary in financial regulation because rigid adherence to rules may not adequately address dynamic market realities or prevent crises.¹¹ The distinction, however, is not absolute, as regulatory powers often contain elements of discretion. The real concern lies in ensuring that discretionary powers are exercised reasonably, proportionately, and in line with the objectives of the enabling law. Where such powers are excessively broad or unchecked, they may give rise to arbitrariness, abuse, or conflict with constitutional principles such as fair hearing and judicial review.

Conversely, insufficient discretionary authority may weaken a regulator's ability to act swiftly in situations that demand urgent intervention, such as preventing bank runs or systemic contagion.¹² Therefore, regulatory and discretionary powers, when balanced, serve complementary functions: regulatory powers establish the legal framework and operational standards, while discretionary powers allow regulators the flexibility to respond effectively to emerging risks and exceptional circumstances. In the context of BOFIA 2020, these powers are designed to equip the CBN with both the structured authority and the flexible judgment required to safeguard Nigeria's financial system against instability, malpractice, and systemic shocks.¹³

3. Legal Framework for Regulatory and Discretionary Powers of the CBN Over Financial Institutions (BOFIA 2020)

3.1 The Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act 2020

The Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020 confers the regulatory and supervisory functions and powers on Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) over banking and business institutions of financial nature in Nigeria.¹⁴ Section 1 of BOFIA seems to rest any argument as to whether the BOFIA is the primary legal instrument for the administration of banks and financial related institutions in Nigeria.¹⁵ The CBN under the BOFIA can delegate its powers on employee or agent(s) so appointed by it.¹⁶ Business relating to banking or financial institutions has to be registered with Corporate Affairs Commission and licensed by CBN under the BOFIA;¹⁷ any person or institution which violates the law commits a crime and upon conviction may face fine or imprisonment or both.¹⁸ The imprisonment may range to 5 years and the fine may be up to #50,000,000.¹⁹ Section 3 of BOFIA deals with the powers of the CBN to grant license to applicant(s) who are desirous of doing banking business in Nigeria; provided the application is made to the Governor of CBN and accompanied with the

⁹ RA MacDonald, *Understanding Regulation by Regulations* <https://www.mcgill.ca/macdonald-symposium/files/macdonald-symposium/cg5_understanding_regulation_by_regulations.pdf> accessed 2 October 2025

¹⁰ KB Mensah, 'Legal control of discretionary powers in Ghana: Lessons from English Administrative Law Theory' *Afrika Focus* (1998)(14)(2)

¹¹ G Okara and C Wigwe, 'Discretionary Powers of the Bench and Law Making' in N Nnadi and others (ed) *Beyond Excellence: A Book of Readings in Honour of Honourable Justice Pascal O. Nnadi, Chief Judge of Imo State Judiciary* (Info Publishers, 2020)

¹² M Quintyn and MW Taylor, *Regulatory and Supervisory Independence and Financial Stability* (IMF Working Paper WP/02;46, 2002)

¹³ B Munir and others, 'Necessity of Discretionary Powers: A Critical Appreciation as a Necessary Evil' *Global Regional Review* (2020)(V)(III)

¹⁴ s.1 Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) 2020; see also the Long Title to the BOFIA 2020.

¹⁵ s.1(1)BOFIA 2020.

¹⁶ s.1(2&3)BOFIA ibid.

¹⁷ s.2(1)BOFIA ibid.

¹⁸ s.2(2)BOFIA ibid.

¹⁹ s.2(2)(a-d)BOFIA ibid.

following documents: a feasibility report for the proposed bank including financial projections for at least five years; a draft copy of the memorandum and articles of association of the proposed bank; a list of the shareholders, directors and principal officers of the proposed bank and their particulars; or on instance of non-interest banking, a list of experts on non-interest banking or finance who will serve as advisory committee of experts; payment of prescribed application fee; and, such other information or documents or reports as the Bank may specify.²⁰

The subscribed shareholders are to subscribe to paid-up shares as indicated by the section 9 of BOFIA. The discretionary powers bequeathed to CBN to issue license or to refuse same and refuse without explanation under s.3(3)BOFIA had been argued hereunder to be contrary to the civil economic rights of the applicant and therefore, inconsistent with the Constitution.²¹Section 5 BOFIA require CBN to vary or revoke licenses conditions of any bank or financial institution in Nigeria. The powers to vary and revoke are to ensure standards and improvements which assure shareholders investment protection and promotion of transparency as well as improved investors confidence. The powers include those of imposing new conditions or additional conditions to stabilise the banking industry.²²Banks are expected under the BOFIA to comply with the regulatory directives issued by CBN on varying or revoking license as well as on fresh and additional conditions to the ones already given in consideration for a license.²³Refusal to comply with fresh or additional conditions attracts fine.²⁴If a director or principal officer of the Bank was involved in the refusal to comply with the CBN fresh or additional conditions, he commits an offence is liable to fine of #2,000,000 or imprisonment for not less than three years or both.²⁵To open or close any branch of any bank, such bank must seek and obtain the CBN or be fined for non-compliance with the provision.²⁶

BOFIA 2020 also contains provisions that impact the choice of procedure for restructuring or reorganization in the resolution of failing banks and they apply irrespective of the provisions of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act 2019.²⁷ In the process of restructuring or reorganizing the business of a failing bank, the Central Bank may, on the application of any of the banks to be affected, order separate meetings of the banks to be summoned in such manner as the Central Bank may direct. Instructively, the Central Bank may approve any such agreement or arrangement if and only if it is satisfied that such agreement or arrangement is not likely to cause a restraint of competition, or tend to create a monopoly in the banking industry;²⁸ the significant shareholders or directors of the bank that results from the agreement or arrangement are not disqualified under the Act; the agreement or arrangement is consistent with public interest, and the bank that results from the agreement or arrangement meets the capital requirements as prescribed under the Act.²⁹ Upon the grant of a new banking licence by the CBN to a bank which results from the agreement or arrangement, all the assets and liabilities of the banks that are parties to the agreement or arrangement shall, by the grant of the new banking licence, be transferred to, and become the assets and liabilities of, the new bank.³⁰

The CBN Governor must give his consent to every reorganisation, restructuring, merger or the like intended to be done by a bank. Such consent of the CBN Governor must be in writing.³¹ Section 7(1) BOFIA is to the effect that the written consent of the CBN governor is required for a valid change of control of a bank, transfer of significant shareholding in bank, sale disposal or transfer in whole or part of business of bank, amalgamation or merger of banks, restructuring, reconstruction or re-organisation of a bank, or transfer of all or part of the business of the bank to any agent.³²The consequence for non-compliance with the section is that the transaction which culminated out of it

²⁰ s.3(1)BOFIA *ibid*.

²¹ See the discussion on Discretionary Powers of CBN Over Financial Institutions Under BOFIA 2020.

²² s.5(1)BOFIA 2020.

²³ s.5(2)BOFIA *ibid*.

²⁴ s.5(5)BOFIA *ibid*.

²⁵ s.5(6)BOFIA *ibid*.

²⁶ s.6 BOFIA *ibid*.

²⁷ s.7(6)BOFIA *ibid*.

²⁸ *ibid*

²⁹ s.7(4)BOFIA *ibid*.

³⁰ s.7(5)BOFIA *ibid*.

³¹ s.7(1)BOFIA *ibid*.

³² s.7(1)(a-e)BOFIA *ibid*.

will be void;³³ that is voidable, if it is not rectified by the CBN.³⁴ A second consequence for non-compliance with s.7(1)BOFIA is liability to fine pursuant to s.7(7)BOFIA. The benefits for complying with the section are the assets and liabilities of the both banks will become one and same.³⁵

Section 12 BOFIA vest the powers to revoke a banking license on the CBN Governor with the approval of the Board vide notice published in *gazette* and or electronically.³⁶ The grounds which may prompt this drastic action by the CBN includes where a bank: ceases to do banking business for which it was licensed for a continuous period of six months or cumulative period of six months within 12 months; liquidated or wound-up or dissolved; fails to fulfil or comply with condition under the license; has not sufficient asset to meet its liabilities; goes into a situation or circumstances or action or inaction which constitutes threat to financial stability; fails to comply with obligations under any law; is undercapitalised; fails to commence banking business 12 months after grant of license; or, fails to comply with sections 9 (on paid-up share capital) or 13 (minimum capital ratio) of BOFIA.³⁷ When a bank's license is revoked under s.12, the CBN Governor will appoint Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) as the liquidator of such bank, and the appointment of NDIC will be as though NDIC was appointed by the Federal High Court.³⁸ Any challenge as to the revocation of license under the provision of s.12 BOFIA will be properly instituted at the Federal High Court and the Court is enjoined to proceed expeditiously.³⁹

The Act provides that any action to challenge the revocation of the license of a bank on any ground whatsoever must be instituted within thirty (30) days from the date of the revocation⁴⁰ at the Federal High Court and such action and any appeal arising therefrom shall be heard and determined on an expedited and accelerated basis.⁴¹ In an interesting turn of events, however, the Act precludes the Court from ordering restoration of a bank's revoked licence and provides that the remedy of any claimant or applicant against the Central Bank or the Governor in any such action, suit or proceedings is limited to monetary compensation not exceeding the equivalent of the value of the paid-up capital of the bank at the time of the revocation of its license.⁴² The view in some quarters is that this new provision will prevent a recurrence of the Savannah Bank Plc. saga where the now-defunct Savannah Bank Plc. was in the court for seven years before its license, which was found to have been revoked in error, was restored to it.⁴³ On the other hand, the constitutionality of this provision may be challenged (and rightly so) on the ground that it purports to preclude the exercise of the judicial powers of the Court under the Constitution.⁴⁴

BOFIA 2020 makes provisions for pre-liquidation avoidance to protect the interests of the creditors of banks and other financial institutions.⁴⁵ A liquidator may set aside transfers and recover assets from: gratuitous transfers to affiliates, insiders or key management personnel of banks or related persons made within 5 years before liquidation; transactions conducted with affiliates, insiders or key management personnel of banks or related persons within five (5) years before liquidation; gratuitous transfers to third parties made within three (3) years before liquidation; transactions at an undervalue made within three (3) years of the liquidation;⁴⁶ transactions based on forged or fraudulent documents executed by the bank to creditors' detriment; actions intended to withhold assets from, or impair the rights of, the bank's creditors within five (5) years before the liquidation; preferences to creditors done one (1) year before the liquidation;⁴⁷ and attachment of security interest within six (6) months

³³ s.7(3)BOFIA

³⁴ s.7(4)BOFIA. *ibid*

³⁵ s.7(5)BOFIA *ibid*.

³⁶ s.12(1)BOFIA *ibid*.

³⁷ s.12(1)(a-j)BOFIA *ibid*.

³⁸ s.12(2)BOFIA *ibid*.

³⁹ s.12(4)BOFIA *ibid*.

⁴⁰ s.12(5)BOFIA *ibid*.

⁴¹ See (n22).

⁴² s.12(6)BOFIA *ibid*.

⁴³ *Savannah Bank Plc v CBN* (2009) 6 NWLR (Pt.1137)237.

⁴⁴ *Njikonye v MTN Nigeria Communications Ltd* (2008) All FWLR (Pt. 413) 1343, 1369 paras. A-B.

⁴⁵ s.73 BOFIA.

⁴⁶ s. 659 of Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA)2020.

⁴⁷ Preference in this context entails transferring the property of a bank to, or for the benefit of, a creditor on account of a debt incurred within one (1) year prior to the date of the liquidation which has the effect of increasing the amount that the creditor would receive in a liquidation of the bank.

before the liquidation. These avoidance provisions are expected to protect the assets of the bank from being depleted in suspicious/duplicitous circumstances before liquidation so as to make assets available for distribution to creditors, subject, of course, to the overarching priority of deposit liabilities i.e repayment of depositors' funds.⁴⁸

BOFIA 2020 also introduces a novel provision that is aimed at improving the regime for the resolution of prospective banking crises in the country. The Act provides that notwithstanding the provisions of any other enactment, relevant agencies (as defined under the Act) shall cooperate with and render such assistance or grant such waivers or forbearances to the CBN, which in the opinion of the Governor are necessary or expedient to resolve a banking crisis.⁴⁹ A banking crisis in this context will occur when two or more of the following conditions occur when: critically distressed banks control 12.5% or more of total assets in the industry; 12.5% or more of total industry deposits are threatened; 12.5% or more of the banking system's total loans are non-performing; or 25% or more of banks have applied for liquidity support above 50% of the aggregate takings from CBN's window or total interbank funds in the market or have been suspended by their settlement banks for failure to meet clearing obligations.⁵⁰

The Act also empowers the CBN Governor to vary the above conditions or prescribe such other conditions as he may deem fit to constitute a banking crisis. Economies all over the world rely on the sanity and stability of their financial system for growth and development. This why it is essential to strengthen the legal framework for insolvency and restructuring in the banking and financial sectors to make it not only domestically safe but also globally competitive; and this is what has been done with the new regime under BOFIA 2020 – ambitiously and admirably too. Banks are simply too important in Nigeria's financial system to be allowed to fail or suffer for too long from the uncertainty of destiny. In that regard, BOFIA 2020 has indeed introduced a worthy and commendable legal framework for banks' insolvency and restructuring in Nigeria in a way that promises to bring sanity, serenity, and stability to the Nigerian financial system going forward.

3.2 The Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act, 2007 is the extant law which established the Central Bank of Nigeria⁵¹ with the objectives to ensure monetary and price stability; issue legal tender currency; maintain external reserves to safeguard the international value of the legal tender currency; promote a sound financial system; and, act as banker and provide economic and financial advice to the Federal Government.⁵² It has all the features of a corporation and can be sued in its corporate name.⁵³ The CBN Act provides that the Bank is to also promote stability and continuity in economic management as an independent body saddled with the responsibility of regulating banks and other financial related institutions in Nigeria.⁵⁴ Section 3 of the CBN Act empowers it to house its headquarters at the Nigeria Federal Capital Territory while it should have branches in each states of the federation; it may appoint agents and correspondences at other nations of the world.⁵⁵ The authorised capital of CBN is completely subscribed by the Federal Government (FG) and any such authorised capital shall also be paid-up by the FG. The CBN board determines any such increment in the capital of the CBN after approval of same by the President of Nigeria.⁵⁶

The CBN Act sets out a system for the governance of CBN. It provides for appointment and qualification of Governor of CBN⁵⁷ and his deputy;⁵⁸ the appointment and qualifications of directors.⁵⁹ Disqualification into the aforementioned positions of Governor, Deputy Governor and Directors are that such a person has become a member of any Federal or State legislative house or

⁴⁸ s.55 BOFIA.

⁴⁹ s.36 BOFIA.

⁵⁰ *ibid*

⁵¹ s.1(1) Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act 2007.

⁵² s.2 CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵³ s.1(2&4) CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁴ s.1(3) CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁵ s.3 CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁶ s.4 CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁷ s.8 CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁸ s.9 CBN Act *ibid*.

⁵⁹ s.10 CBN Act *ibid*.

joins the employment of any Bank under the BOFIA.⁶⁰ The disqualification from the offices includes incidences where the person becomes of unsound mind because of his health or that the person becomes incapable of performing his duties;⁶¹ or the person is convicted of a criminal offence except for traffic offence committed in the cause of the discharge of his official duties;⁶² is guilty of misconduct relating to his duties;⁶³ disqualified or suspended from practicing his profession; or is bankrupt; or the President removes him with support of 2/3 of senate.⁶⁴ The foregoing is significant in determination whether any regulation made by the CBN or the exercise of discretion by it conform to the law in force at the time. If the person said to be acting for or on the behalf of CBN is deficient, would he be said to have actually acted on behalf of the CBN? It is argued that a person acting for CBN must possess the requisite qualifications and not be disqualified in any means by the extant laws. The CBN Act established the Monetary Policy Committee with the mandate to formulate monetary and credit policy within the CBN.⁶⁵ The membership of the Monetary Policy Committee, their qualification, tenure, disqualification, remuneration are subjected to the same terms as are stipulated for Director.⁶⁶ Nigeria currency is designated into naira and kobo;⁶⁷ CBN determines exchange rate for Naira vide suitable mechanism.⁶⁸ The CBN has powers to liquidity management; it may carry out open market operations for maintaining monetary stability in the economy of the country. It can issue, place, sell, repurchase, amortise or redeem securities.⁶⁹ It can subscribe to or hold and sell shares of any corporation or company or debentures with the approval or authority of the FG for promoting development of money or capital market.⁷⁰ The CBN has powers to function as a bank with all consequential duties thereto.⁷¹ It has powers to require information from persons and institutions on matters touching, concerning and affecting the economy of Nigeria; it has powers to issue guidelines to any person or institution under its supervision.⁷² CBN is the banker's bank in Nigeria and outside Nigeria.⁷³ CBN has powers to require reserve of certain minimum deposit from other banks to be kept in its head office.⁷⁴ It has powers to make and alter rules and regulations for the good order and management of CBN. It has powers to license and regulate credit bureaux and other financial institutions.⁷⁵

4. Institutional Framework for Regulatory and Discretionary Powers of the CBN Over Financial Institutions (BOFIA 2020)

4.1 Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)

Central Bank of Nigeria is charged under s.1(1) of BOFIA with the administration of the Act.⁷⁶ The CBN is to ensure compliance of all banks and financial institutions with the provisions of the BOFIA. It issues license, can revoke licenses, enforces compliance with the provisions of BOFIA and other related laws and guidelines made thereto. The powers of the CBN to remove and appoint a director can be deduced from the combined reading of ss. 33 and 34(1)(2) of the BOFIA. Essentially, the CBN, under s.33, has the power to investigate the affairs of a bank where: a director, shareholder, creditor or depositor applies to the CBN; the bank is carrying on business in a way that is detrimental to the interest of the depositors or creditors; the bank does not have sufficient assets to cover its liabilities to the public; the bank has contravened any provision of the BOFIA or a relevant law; or where it is in the interest of the public to do so.

⁶⁰ s.11(1) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶¹ s.11(2)(a) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶² s.11(2)(b) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶³ s.11(2)(c) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁴ s.11(2)(d-f) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁵ s.12(1&3) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁶ s.12(4) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁷ s.15 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁸ s.16 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁶⁹ s.30(a) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷⁰ s.31 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷¹ s.32 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷² s.33(1)(a&b) CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷³ s.41 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷⁴ s.45 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷⁵ s.57 CBN Act *ibid.*

⁷⁶ s.1(1) BOFIA.

Based on the investigations conducted under s.33, if the CBN is satisfied that the bank is liable in respect of the issue it was investigated for¹⁰, the CBN may exercise the powers conferred on it under s.34(2) which includes the power to (notwithstanding any law or the memorandum and articles of the bank) remove a director and appoint any person in his stead and stipulate the amount to be paid to that director as remuneration. Under the BOFIA, “other financial institution” refer to individuals, groups or companies that engage in the business of discount houses, bureau de change, finance company, money brokerage, foreign exchange purchase, international money transfer services, mortgage refinance or guarantee company, finance holding company or payment service providers, factoring, project financing, debt administration, equipment leasing, fund and investment management, private ledger services, and local purchases order financing. Under the BOFIA, where the CBN is satisfied that a company classified as an “other financial institution” is in “a grave situation”, the CBN may exercise the powers granted to it under s.34, including the power to remove and appoint a director.

4.2 Financial Services Regulation Coordinating Committee

The Financial Services Regulation Coordinating Committee is established under s.43(1) of the CBN Act; it consist of Governor of CBN as Chairman, Managing Director, Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, Director-General Securities and Exchange Commission, the Commissioner for Insurance, Registrar-General of Corporate Affairs Commission, and a Director representing Ministry of Finance.⁷⁷ This Committee is to co-ordinate supervision of financial institutions particularly conglomerates. They are to ensure reduction of arbitrage opportunities created by differing regulation, ensure that supervisory authorities maintain standards for the economy; deliberate problems encountered by any Committee member in relationship with any financial institution; eliminate information gap; articulate strategies for promotion of safe, sound and efficient practices by financial intermediaries; and, deliberate on other issues.⁷⁸

4.3 Federal High Court

The Federal High Court is the proper Court to hear and determine matters of banking in Nigeria.⁷⁹Section 12(4)BOFIA also enjoins the Court to conduct expeditious hearing and determination of matters challenging the revocation of license of a bank. This could be to check if BOFIA was complied with or if there was an irregularity in the exercise of discretion by the CBN. The action against any revocation of banking license is maintainable only if it was filed within 30 days from the date of the publication of such revocation.⁸⁰For example, On 18 August 2021, the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) obtained an interim freezing order against the bank accounts of some Fintech companies at the Federal High Court, Abuja. The court issued the said order on the back of an ex-parte application filed by the CBN urging the court to freeze the bank accounts of the companies for a period of 180 days pending investigations by the CBN.⁸¹ As basis for obtaining the freezing order – the CBN alleged that the Fintech companies had played roles in 'illegal foreign exchange (FX) trading, accessing/ Introduction 6 September 2021 procuring of foreign exchange, foreign securities and cryptocurrency via their bank accounts, from the Nigerian FX Market via Bureaux de Change (BDCs), International Money Transfer Operators (IMTOs) and Commodity Exporters', in contravention of the Foreign Exchange (Monitoring and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act (FEMMPA), the CBN Foreign Exchange Manual 2018, and the CBN Circular to banks prohibiting financial institutions from trading in cryptocurrencies.⁸² Remarkably, CBN's allegations against the Fintech companies do not constitute a crime under the FEMMPA relied upon and the allegations would seem to only relate to breaches or infractions of the CBN FX Manual 2018 and the CBN circular(s) prohibiting financial institutions from trading in cryptocurrencies.

Section 97 of the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act, 2020 empowers the CBN to apply ex-parte to the Federal High Court, for an order freezing any account where it has reasons to believe that the transactions undertaken in any account with any bank or other financial institutions are such as may involve the commission of any criminal offence under any law. The proviso to subsections 3

⁷⁷s.43(2)(a-f)CBN Act *ibid*.

⁷⁸ s.44(a-f) CBN Act *ibid*.

⁷⁹ s.251CFRN

⁸⁰ s.12(5) BOFIA *ibid*.

⁸¹ See copy of Motion ex parte filed by the CBN on 4 August 2021 and order of court granted on 17 August 2021.

⁸² CBN Circular referenced TED/FEM/FPC/GEN/01/012 and BSD/DIR/PUB/LAB/014/001 dated 5 February 2021 and 01 July 2015.

further allows the CBN to obtain such ex-parte order in furtherance of ongoing investigations where the allegations relate to contravention of the provisions of the BOFIA or any other law administered by the CBN. If for any reason the investigation is not concluded within the period stipulated in the order, the CBN may apply for an extension of the order.⁸³ However, it bears mentioning that this power of the Governor to apply for freezing orders and that of the court to grant such orders, is restricted to only where the CBN Governor believes that the transactions under investigations involve an actual commission of a criminal offence under a written law; not merely a breach/infraction of a CBN directive/manual. In the case of *Paulson v State*⁸⁴ it was held that an act can only be crime where it violate a written law or regulations made thereto. It seems correct that such act must not be a mere violation of guidelines but law or regulations.

It was argued that while the CBN may have obtained the freezing order based on an alleged breach of its FX Manual, this was inconsistent with s.36 (12) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) which provides that an act will not constitute a crime unless it is clearly defined in, and the punishment for the act is prescribed by a written law.⁸⁵ It therefore follows from the above provision of the constitution that as a matter of law, a person or corporation can only be punished for an offence where the definition and punishment for that offence are contained in a written law. A written law is a law enacted by the National Assembly or the law of a state and the CBN FX Manual, regrettably, fails to qualify as a written law for this purpose.⁸⁶ Contrary to the allegations of the CBN, it seems that none of the infractions alleged against the Fintech companies form part of the offences provided under the FEMMPA or any other extant law(s). It was further argued that the Constitution also presumes the innocence of an accused person until proven guilty,⁸⁷ and that presumption implies that the fundamental rights of an accused person (including the right to own and use property) cannot and should not be infringed upon beyond the permissible limits stipulated in the Constitution. While the CBN argues that the actions of the Fintech companies continue to undermine the CBN's efforts to maintain a stable foreign exchange regime and that the Fintech companies are engaged in illegal activities, it fails to satisfactorily tie the alleged activities of the Fintech companies to any known criminal offence as would support the issuance of the freezing orders by the court.

4.4 Special Tribunals for the Enforcement and Recovery of Eligible Loans

The Special Tribunals for the Enforcement and Recovery of Eligible Loans is established by the BOFIA under s.102(1) thereof.⁸⁸ The Tribunal is tasked with the resolution of actions for the enforcement and recovery of eligible loans and actions connected with the enforcement of security or guarantee, or attachment of any assets under an eligible loan made by any bank.⁸⁹ For clarity, the Act defines as an eligible loan as any credit facility, overdraft, loan, or risk asset of at least NGN25, 000,000:00 (Twenty-Five Million Naira) or such other amount as may be prescribed by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) which repayment obligations have become due for not less than ninety (90) days and which has been designated by the CBN Governor as being eligible for enforcement and recovery before the Tribunal. To properly discharge its functions, the Tribunal is empowered to (a) grant an injunction or appoint a liquidator in appropriate cases; (b) make orders to enforce security or guarantee or attachment of assets under an eligible loan; (c) make an order of mandamus, prohibition or certiorari, including against an officer or authority of the Federation; (d) upon an ex parte application, before or after the filing of the action for debt recovery, grant custody and/or possession of a debtor's movable or immovable property to a financial institution pending the hearing and determination of a debt recovery action; (e) upon an ex parte application, before or after the filing of the action for debt recovery, grant an interlocutory order freezing a debtor's account(s) pending the hearing and determination of a debt recovery action; (f) summon and examine persons before it.⁹⁰

⁸³ s.97(4) BOFIA *ibid*.

⁸⁴ *Paulson v State* (2012) 6 NWLR (Pt.1297) 456.

⁸⁵ *Prince Joshua Paulson v The State* (2012) 6 NWLR (Pt.1297) 456.

⁸⁶ A written law has been defined in the case of *Okafor v Lagos State Govt* (2017) 4 NWLR (Pt.1556) 404 to be an Act of the National Assembly or the law of the State.

⁸⁷ s.36(5)CFRN 1999.

⁸⁸ s.102(1) BOFIA *ibid*.

⁸⁹ s.115(1) BOFIA *ibid*.

⁹⁰ s.122(2) BOFIA.

Overall, the creation of the Credit Tribunal for accelerated hearing and resolution of loan-related matters is a laudable development that is expected will help reduce the country's non-performing loan portfolio and impact positively on the financial health of the banking sector in Nigeria.

4.5 Banking Sector Resolution Fund / Bail-In Tool

The Banking Sector Resolution Fund/Bail-In Tool is established under s.74 BOFIA to give support to distressed or failing banks.⁹¹ BOFIA 2020 also introduces the (Banking Sector) Resolution Fund to give support (regulatory and financial) to failing or distressed banks. The resolution fund will be funded annually by the CBN and the commercial banks and managed by the CBN who will determine the start date.⁹² The fund aims to eradicate or, at least, minimize recourse to public funds for the resolution of crises in the banking sector and of failing or failed banks. With the creation of this resolution fund, BOFIA 2020 has opted for the "bail-in" option as against the usual (but undesirable and often problematic) "bail-out" option.

The objectives of the Fund includes: paying the operating costs of bridge banks; paying the costs of transferring the whole or part of the business of a bank under a resolution measure; providing loans, overdrafts or other credit facilities to a bridge bank or a bank under resolution; paying the professional fees and costs (e.g. legal, advisory, valuation, etc.) incurred in a resolution measure; other purposes in support of such resolution measures as may be prescribed by the CBN Governor; and paying the cost of administering and managing the Fund.⁹³ The Act also gives the CBN the power to debit, for the benefit of the Fund, the account of any bank which fails to pay its quota into the fund. Also, the Act provides for stringent sanctions and penalties for directors and officers of banks whose fraud or negligent action triggers recourse to the Resolution Fund to resolve or otherwise fund a bank. Apart from all the above, in furthering its goal of maintaining financial stability and minimizing systemic risk, the Act has introduced further banking sector resolution tools. These include: suspension of contractual termination rights tool. BOFIA 2020 empowers the Bank to suspend the right of contractual parties with a bank to exercise early contractual termination rights where the bank is the subject, or a proposed subject, of a resolution measure.⁹⁴

Termination rights can also be suspended where the counterparty is an entity that is part of the same group as a bank and the bank is the subject, or proposed subject, of a resolution measure; the contractual termination right is exercisable if the bank becomes insolvent or is in a certain financial condition; and the entity's obligation under the contract is guaranteed or supported by the bank.⁹⁵ Furthermore, notwithstanding any provision of a law or contract, any purported exercise of contractual termination right during the period of suspension is void.⁹⁶ Nevertheless, a contractual termination right can still be exercised during the period of suspension with the CBN's prior written consent.⁹⁷ Secondly, asset separation tool. BOFIA 2020 empowers the Bank to transfer the assets of a bank to one or more private asset management vehicles (PAMVs) to manage to maximize their value for an eventual sale or organized and measured winding-up.⁹⁸ By so doing, the Act allows the CBN to isolate the "bad" assets of the bank in an asset management vehicle if current market conditions do not justify immediate liquidation. Importantly, the CBN can exercise this power without having to obtain the consent of the shareholders of the bank or any third party other than the PAMV, and without complying with any procedural requirements under any law or contract.⁹⁹ Similarly, to protect the transferred assets from interference, the Act prevents the shareholders and creditors of a bank from enforcing any right, judgment or claim against those assets.¹⁰⁰ The Act further provides that the PAMV does not owe the shareholders or creditors of the bank any duty or responsibility and shall not be liable to them for the acts and omissions of its management in the discharge of their duties unless for fraud or gross misconduct which directly affects the rights of such shareholders or

⁹¹ s.74 BOFIA.

⁹² ss.74-104 BOFIA *ibid*.

⁹³ s.78 BOFIA *ibid*.

⁹⁴ s.40(1)BOFIA.

⁹⁵ *ibid*

⁹⁶ s.40(6)BOFIA.

⁹⁷ s.40(7)BOFIA.

⁹⁸ s.41(1,3&6)BOFIA.

⁹⁹ s.41(2)BOFIA.

¹⁰⁰ s.41(5)BOFIA.

creditors.¹⁰¹Thirdly, sale of business tool .BOFIA 2020 empowers the CBN to sell the securities, assets, and liabilities of a failing bank to a third party after having taken reasonable steps to obtain “commercial” (fair) terms in the circumstances.¹⁰²

5. The Regulatory and Discretionary Powers of The CBN Over Financial Institutions Under BOFIA 2020

5.1 Regulatory Powers of CBN Over Financial Institutions Under BOFIA 2020

The regulatory powers of the CBN under s.3 BOFIA is to issue license to deserving applicant institution where it meets the requirements stipulated by that section of BOFIA. The law is well settled in s.3(1) BOFIA that any person desiring to undertake banking business in Nigeria shall apply in writing to the Governor for the grant of a licence and shall accompany the application with a feasibility report plus financial projections for five years; draft memorandum and articles of association, list of directors and shareholders as well as principal officers, experts in non-interest banking if the application for the license in that regards, application fee and such other documents or information or report the Board or Governor may require.¹⁰³Section 5 BOFIA bequeaths the powers to vary or revoke banking licenses on the CBN Governor.¹⁰⁴The powers to vary or revoke license *simpliciter* are regulatory power.¹⁰⁵They are vested to make for innovations in the industry and to improve and create opportunities for up-coming businesses. It is made to standardise and improve investors/shareholders confidence in their investments in the banking industry. It is part of the obligations of a bank to inform CBN when they want to open a branch or close same.¹⁰⁶Failure to disclose the opening of a branch or the closure attracts fine of #5,000,000.¹⁰⁷The CBN Governor may order closure or opening of a branch of bank.¹⁰⁸

Core among the mandate of the CBN under the BOFIA is to ensure that troubled banks are saved because of depositors monies in such banks to avoid the incidences of great depression and great recession. Globally, the role of financial regulators and supervisors is to maintain a safe and stable financial system within the broad spectrum of macroeconomic stability. Financial stability gained importance in the early 1930s during the Great Depression era in the United States. Despite the efforts of financial regulators and supervisors to maintain financial stability, evidence abounds that several bank failures have occurred across the globe since the Great Depression.¹⁰⁹The International Association of Deposit Insurers defined a troubled bank as a bank that has, or will have, impaired liquidity or solvency unless there is a major improvement in its financial resources, risk profile, strategic business direction, risk management capabilities and/or quality of management.” Other literature describe a bank as “troubled” or “failing” when its indicators of financial soundness begin to deteriorate due to unsound practices or systemic factors.¹¹⁰ Generally speaking, a troubled financial institution exhibits one or all of the following characteristics: gross undercapitalization in relation to the level of operation; secondly, high level of classified loans and advances; thirdly, illiquidity reflected in the inability to meet customer’s cash withdrawals; fourthly, low earnings resulting from huge operational losses and weak management as reflected by poor credit quality, inadequate internal controls, high rate of frauds and forgeries, and labor turnover.

In the Nigerian banking industry, s.34 BOFIA and the Supervisory Intervention Framework for Nigerian Banks (2011) encapsulates criteria for recognizing that a bank is tending towards failure. The BOFIA describes a bank as failing if such as bank: (a) is likely to become unable to meet its obligations under the Act; (b) is about to suspend payment to any extent; (c) is insolvent; or (d) where,

¹⁰¹ s.41(8)BOFIA.

¹⁰² s.42 BOFIA.

¹⁰³ s.3(1)(a-f) BOFIA 2020.

¹⁰⁴ s.5 BOFIA *ibid*.

¹⁰⁵ *ibid*.

¹⁰⁶ s.6 BOFIA *ibid*.

¹⁰⁷ s.6(4)BOFIA *ibid*.

¹⁰⁸ s.6(5)BOFIA *ibid*.

¹⁰⁹ The Great Recession was the sharp decline in economic activity during the late 2000s. It is considered the most significant downturn since the Great Depression. The term Great Recession applies to both the U.S. recession, officially lasting from December 2007 to June 2009, and the ensuing global recession in 2009.

¹¹⁰ H. Mustafa, ‘Restructuring and Reenergizing Troubled Banks: The Role of Bank Supervisors and Regulators’ *NDIC Quarterly* (2021)(36)(3&4)124&125.

after an examination, the CBN is satisfied that the bank is in a grave situation. The Supervisory Intervention Framework for Nigerian Banks, on the other hand, leverages financial soundness indicators of capital, liquidity, asset quality, and earnings as the basis for identifying a troubled bank.¹¹¹ The failure of a financial institution can destabilize the domestic economy and imperil public confidence in the financial system. The responsibility of the Regulator and Supervisors, therefore, in detecting early and taking proactive steps to remedy the indicators of possible failure of a bank cannot be over-emphasized. Having provided a contextual perspective in the preceding section on the characteristics which a troubled bank exhibits, this section discusses the powers and tools available to the CBN in the legislative and regulatory frameworks to nurture a failing or troubled bank back to financial soundness.

The BOFIA 2020 was enacted to strengthen the regulatory and supervisory framework of the Nigerian banking industry, the key of which is prioritizing the rescue of troubled institutions to avert eventual failure. The Act provides a range of options and tools for the CBN to deploy in preventing the failure of a bank. Section 33 BOFIA empowers the Governor to make an order for a special examination of the books and affairs of a bank can to commissioned to detect beforehand concerns that could lead to the failure of the bank if not remedied early. Section 34 (2) (a-i) is on the written order of the Governor that the following restrictive and holding actions can be imposed on a bank in troubled waters with the aim of restoring the bank to soundness. Prohibition of further extension of credit facilities:- troubled banks can be stopped from granting new loans and loan enhancements where credit administration is weak, resulting in the build-up of non-performing loans and the gradual erosion of capital. Suspension of any payment or delivery obligations on a contract:- contractual obligations to make payments can temporarily be suspended to prevent pressure on the bank's liquidity. Removal of any director, managers, or officers as the CBN may deem necessary to strengthen corporate governance; appointment of any person or persons as directors of the bank; and appointment of Advisers for the bank.

Section 34 BOFIA further empowers the CBN to: require third party service providers to the bank to continue in that capacity for such period as may be specified in the order; and acquire the shares of the troubled bank to a level that confers control on the CBN.¹¹² Regulatory forbearances are the discretionary decision of the CBN to refrain from applying certain regulatory requirements or reducing the scope of regulation to prevent contagion that may lead to a financial crisis. It can also be described as the decision by the CBN to grant additional time to a troubled bank, to meet regulatory requirements without applying relevant provisions of the law, including sanctions and penalties. Regulatory forbearance is exclusively at the discretion of the CBN to exercise when prevailing circumstances do not favor the application of rescue options or tools on an ailing bank. Other factors that influence the grant of regulatory forbearances are the cost of resolution, political pressure, concerns about the overall health of the financial system. Another regulatory power of the CBN relates to dormant accounts. Section 72 of BOFIA 2020 provides that account balances in banks which have not been operated for a year or period specified by CBN should be transferred to a special register in a bank. Where such funds remain unclaimed after 10 years, they are to be transferred to the CBN. However, the banks are required to try to notify the account holder by various means, including placing an advert in two national newspapers, before transferring the funds to the CBN.¹¹³ Interestingly, the duration stipulated in BOFIA 2020 differs from that of a similar provision introduced by Finance Act, 2020 establishing the Unclaimed Funds Trust Fund ('the Trust Fund') which will be supervised by the Debt Management Office (DMO) and governed by a Council co-headed by the MoF and a private sector co-chair. Under Finance Act, 2020, dormant funds are to be transferred to the Trust Fund after 6 years. Given that Finance Act, 2020 was enacted after BOFIA 2020, it may be safe to assume that the "later in time" rule would apply and, consequently, dormant funds would be transferred to the Trust Fund, after 6 years of dormancy as provided in Finance Act, 2020. However, it is important to explicitly resolve the discrepancies between the two laws to avoid confusion as banks are obliged to comply with BOFIA, being the primary law regulating their industry. The new amendments introduced in BOFIA 2020 have expanded the CBN's discretion and

¹¹¹ s.34 BOFIA ibid

¹¹² s.34 BOFIA.

¹¹³ s.27 BOFIA

consolidated its supervisory role over the banking operations of players in the financial system from what obtained under BOFIA 2004. These changes should, therefore, strengthen the financial services industry and promote transparency and integrity in the industry

BOFIA 2020 prioritizes the prevention of banks from getting distressed, over rescuing them, which is very commendable. The expansion of the CBN's powers and the creation of some of the new tools introduced by the Act should help to prevent bank failures and other systemic issues. However, it is doubtful if the CBN can realistically enforce some of the listed measures. For instance, it may be unrealistic to compel third party service providers to continue rendering services to an illiquid bank. Such arrangements are contractual and the CBN may have to offer affected vendors some guarantee of receiving payment for their services.¹¹⁴ Another tool available to the CBN is the option to transfer a bank or any part of it to private third party buyers (which expressly contradicts the constitutional prohibitions against expropriation of private property), and to employ any other intervention method the CBN deems fit. While these are far-reaching measures, it is expected that the CBN will judiciously exercise its powers to sustain investors' confidence in our financial system regulation. Section 54 of BOFIA 2020 recognizes the legal enforceability of netting arrangements by banks, and limits to the powers of liquidators to unravel such transactions. Prior to BOFIA 2020, there was no Act which clearly recognized the enforceability of netting transactions in Nigeria's national payment system. Rather, the legal rules on netting relied on the CBN's generic payment system oversight powers pursuant to the CBN Act.¹¹⁵ Due to this, there had been some payment system risk because of the absence of clear statutory provisions on netting arrangements and other payment concepts. The recently enacted Companies' Allied Matters Act, 2020 also included provisions on netting arrangements to mitigate credit and settlement risks. This amendment ensures that netting arrangements have a clear basis in the law and gives legal certainty to parties to such transactions. Also, the amendment would strengthen the payment system and protect it from settlement risk. Currently, Nigeria does not have a dedicated payment system law, and this is a gap that needs to be addressed. However, the amendment stipulated under section 54 of the BOFIA, in addition to CBN's generic power to oversee the payment system pursuant to the CBN Act, should act as effective stop-gap measure in the meantime¹¹⁶

The effect of s.57 BOFIA is that it now recognizes the CBN as a regulator of all entities providing financial services in Nigeria. The section also lists the types of entities overseen by the CBN and leaves the list open-ended to ensure flexibility. Some of the specified financial service institutions include discount houses, bureaux de change, credit bureaux, finance companies or money brokerage firms, international money transfer service firms, mortgage refinance companies, mortgage guarantee companies, credit guarantee firms, financial holding companies or payment services providers. Further, the section provides that the CBN would oversee any company whose objects in its Memorandum of Association include equipment leasing, factoring, project financing, debt administration, investment management, private ledger services, export finance, and any other company that the CBN may designate in future.¹¹⁷ However, a concern may be the issue of over-regulation of some of the other financial service providers, such as the FinTechs. Currently, the CBN regulates FinTechs that undertake payments and other financial services, while the Security Exchange Commission (SEC)'s FinTech and Innovation Office (FINO) seeks to regulate FinTechs at large. Given the collaborative and dynamic working relationship between the CBN and SEC, the two regulators should jointly determine which of them would be best to exercise primary oversight over any class of firms, and to cede ground to the other where necessary. This is important to ensure that the administrative costs and regulatory compliance burdens of these companies do not increase so much as to stunt their growth.

There are the issues around suspension of the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (FCCPA). Section 65 of the Act removes products and services in the financial services sector from the purview of anti-trust rules set in the FCCPA. This means that the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission (FCCPC), going forward, will no longer oversee any function, act,

¹¹⁴ KPMG Nigeria, BOFIA 2020: Impact on the Financial Services Industry (KPMG, April 2021)5.

¹¹⁵ s.54 BOFIA.

¹¹⁶ s.54 BOFIA *ibid.*

¹¹⁷ s.57 BOFIA *ibid.*

financial products and services provided by banks and other entities licensed by the CBN. Interestingly, BOFIA 2020 provides that mergers and acquisitions and any other forms of business re-organizations by banks and other organizations regulated by the CBN, are to be conducted in accordance with the FCCPA. However, it is the CBN that is to exercise regulatory oversight over the process, instead of the FCCPC. This ensures that the CBN has total oversight over banks and their operations. In addition to its supervisory role, the CBN may provide additional guidelines on business combinations within the financial services sector. The change introduced by BOFIA 2020 that the CBN should have total oversight over business re-organization and competition issues in the financial services sector is commendable. However, the suspension of anti-trust rules on financial products and services may influence the wider Nigerian economy. Competition rules were put in place to remove monopolistic tendencies which are harmful to consumers and, ultimately, the Nigerian economy. It is the FCCPC that has the specialized skills required to oversee competition issues, mergers and other such transactions. Thus, the CBN is encouraged to lean on the FCCPC's expertise in preventing and curtailing anti-competitive tendencies in the financial services sector. Section 74 of BOFIA 2020 introduced the Banking Sector Resolution Fund ('the Fund'). This will provide liquidity to the CBN's resolution measures by providing overdrafts or credit facilities and funding bridge banks, among others. The Fund is to complement Asset Management Corporation of Nigeria (AMCON)'s activities, but it is not intended to replace AMCON. The Fund is to be domiciled with the CBN and managed by a Board of Trustees. The Governor of the CBN, with the approval of the CBN's Board, is to determine the commencement date of the Fund.¹¹⁸

The contributors to the Fund are the CBN, NDIC, the banks and other financial institutions. Initial commitments of 10 billion and 4 billion, respectively, are expected from the CBN and the NDIC. Annually, the banks and other financial entities are to be surcharged with a levy payable by 30 April of each subsequent year which are tax deductible. Any bank or entity which fails to make its contribution to the Fund would be prohibited from paying out dividends to its shareholders or bonuses to its employees. The introduction of the Fund and its corporate governance measures are commendable. Also, the Fund will provide the CBN with another tool to resolve issues of any distressed bank. The funding arrangements should also reduce taxpayers' cost in rescuing ailing banks over the long run. However, the annual contributions required from the banks and other entities will increase their cost of doing business, strain their resources and cash flows, and increase their administrative compliance burdens. This point is important as banks are already levied to the Banking Sector Resolution Cost Fund, pursuant to the AMCON Amendment Act 2015 ('AMCON Fund'). The AMCON Fund was due to lapse in 2020, but it is liable to be extended by the National Assembly for another 5 years. Given the similarity of the names, it appears that BOFIA 2020 has come to give more permanence to the previously tenured AMCON Fund. A consolation to the banks may be that the higher costs is a collective pain necessary to preserve the integrity of the system, which would protect them and the larger public over the long term.

5.2 Discretionary Powers of CBN Over Financial Institutions Under BOFIA 2020

Section 3(1)(f) BOFIA grants discretionary powers to the CBN as to require other information or documents or reports from applicants who desire to own a bank in Nigeria or run other financial institution regulated under the BOFIA.¹¹⁹ The discretion expected under the paragraph does not and will not be interpreted to overshadow or overwhelm the provisions of the preceding paragraph of the section. It will only be properly interpreted to mean other complimentary documents or information or reports. It is argued that it will not include conditions or the doing of impossibility by an applicant or such other conditions which are not envisaged under the section thereof. It is not a blanket discretion which could be exercised at the whims and caprices of those who are saddled with regulatory functions. Section 3(3) BOFIA is literally to the effect that the Governor of CBN can issue license or refuse to issue license and he does not owe any person or applicant explanation as to why he refused after the applicant had complied with all the requirements of the BOFIA.¹²⁰ If this provision on s.3(3) BOFIA is to be properly interpreted, it should be that the entirety of the purposes of banking or establishment of financial institution may be jeopardised or for national security will ground such

¹¹⁸ s.74 BOFIA.

¹¹⁹ s.3(1)(f) BOFIA *ibid*.

¹²⁰ s.3(3) BOFIA 2020.

refusal. It appears to this dissertation that the discretion to refuse and not give any reason for such refusal after conditions precedent to acquisition of such license has been fulfilled will to say the least preposterous, unacceptable and unjustifiable in democratic civilised society. Does section (3)(3) BOFIA not constitute a determination of civil rights and obligations envisaged under s.36 of the Nigerian Constitution? Is the civil rights to own bank or financial institution not being threatened (with refusal without explanation) by the refusing authority as to why such civil economic right should be abridged with impunity? Section 3(3) BOFIA seems to violate the constitutional provision on making available a copy of such decision to any person whose right is determined in any administration board/tribunal decision.¹²¹ Section 36(2)(b) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended provides that the decision of the Board under s.3(3) BOFIA should not contain provisions which makes it final and conclusive; that is “contains no provision making the determination of the administering authority final or conclusive.”

The draftsmen in section (3)BOFIA thought too much about the Board or the Governor of CBN as to arrogate to him powers beyond what the Constitution of the Country had provided. The Constitution is supreme and its provisions binds all authorities including the Board aforementioned and the CBN Governor; and if Acts of the National Assembly empowered the CBN Governor contrary to the Constitution, s.3(3)BOFIA will, in the position of this dissertation, bow to s.36(2)(b)CFRN for attempting to put finality on decisions which affects civil economic rights of citizens. Discretion under s.3(3)BOFIA must be exercised in favour of the applicant bank where it will not clog competition nor create monopoly in the banking industry. The power of the CBN to impose fresh or additional conditions to the grant of a license is to this dissertation discretionary. It follows that such should be exercised upon consideration of facts, positions and effects. The BOFIA would not contemplate that the exercise of such discretion should be arbitrary or selective. It should be based on objectivity and standards set on equality basis. The CBN has powers to order opening or closure of branch of a bank depending on what the Governor or board deems right even without the application by such bank.¹²²

The law is now trite that where a bank intends to do merger or any form of rearrangement intra or inter-bank, it must inform the CBN or the CBN may subsequently approve of such arrangement. CBN has the discretion to order separate meetings where the banks concerned will make their arrangements to their organisation's best interest or the CBN may desire to seat over the meeting for the merger if it has reason to so do.¹²³ Section 12 of BOFIA 2020 introduces additional circumstances under which banking licences may be revoked, and significantly expands the CBN's discretion in exercising such powers. Also, the Act prohibits the Federal High Court (FHC) from restoring any bank's licence where the CBN has revoked such licence. However, an aggrieved party can only be granted monetary compensation, which would not be more than the value of paid-up capital held in the bank. Would it not be said that s.12 BOFIA tends to oust the powers of the FHC in exercise of its constitutional mandate to determine between civil rights and obligations of persons before it? The expanded circumstances for licence revocation should safeguard the system by curbing any reckless tendency by any bank and ensure stability of the Nigerian financial institutions. However, the cap placed on reliefs which the FHC may grant to aggrieved parties when there is a licence revocation may be viewed negatively by the court itself. Generally, courts do not take kindly to provisions which seek to restrict their judicial powers. Consequently, the FHC may ignore the limitation and grant other reliefs by relying on its general powers under the Constitution. Relatedly, where foreign investors are involved, the cap on monetary compensation payable to parties could potentially contradict the sovereign guarantee provided by the Federal Government to foreign investors in Section 25 of the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Act (NIPC Act). This may need to be revisited so as not to discourage foreign direct investment in Nigeria's financial services sector.

6. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the regulatory and discretionary powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria under BOFIA 2020 underscore the critical role of the apex bank in safeguarding financial stability, protecting

¹²¹ s.36(7)Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended.

¹²² s.6(5)(a&b)BOFIA *ibid*.

¹²³ s.7(2)BOFIA *ibid*.

depositors, and ensuring the integrity of Nigeria's banking and financial system. While its regulatory powers provide a structured legal framework for licensing, supervision, and enforcement of prudential standards, its discretionary powers allow for flexible and timely intervention in response to dynamic economic realities and institutional failures. However, the breadth of these powers necessitates a careful balance between efficiency and accountability to prevent arbitrariness and abuse. Ultimately, BOFIA 2020 equips the CBN with robust tools to align Nigeria's financial regulation with international best practices, but the effective exercise of these powers must be guided by transparency, proportionality, and respect for the rule of law to maintain public confidence and foster sustainable growth in the financial sector.

It is recommended that while the CBN should continue to exercise its regulatory and discretionary powers under BOFIA 2020 to preserve financial stability, such powers should be exercised with greater transparency, accountability, and adherence to due process. There is a need for clearer statutory guidelines to limit excessive discretion, periodic judicial and legislative oversight to check potential abuse, and enhanced stakeholder engagement to ensure that regulatory actions reflect both prudential concerns and the interests of financial institutions and the wider economy. Strengthening internal governance within the CBN, adopting international best practices such as the Basel Core Principles, and ensuring consistent communication of policy objectives would further enhance the credibility and effectiveness of its regulatory framework.